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The rotavirus transcriptome.

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Infectious diarrheal disease is a major medical problem worldwide. Rotavirus is a major contributor to infectious diarrheal disease. We studied the rotavirus transcriptome by measuring total transcription in the peripheral blood in humans infected with rotavirus *in vivo*. We describe here silencing and activation of cytokines and chemokines in the blood resulting from rotavirus infection in children. IL-16 production was a major molecular consequence of rotavirus infection *in vivo*, together with activation of IL-17RA and IL-6R. Induction of IL-16, IL-17RA and IL-6R was accompanied by suppression of CXCL8. Rotavirus infection silenced expression of CD83 and CD69. The integrin-linked kinase ILK was activated by rotavirus infection. In small intestine organoids, infection with rotavirus resulted in activation of sensors RIG-I and Zbp1, and induction of interferons Ifn1 and Ifn2.

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